

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF SAWDUST–MARBLE DUST FILLED EPOXY BIOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract— This paper presents sawdust–marble dust epoxy biocomposites made with a fixed 40 wt.% epoxy binder. Four formulations were tested for density, water absorption, strength, hardness and wear. SD40MD20 showed the best overall balance, including 1.78 g/cm³ density, 2.85% water absorption, 57.538 MPa compressive strength, 49.87 MPa flexural strength, 63 RHN hardness and the lowest wear rate. The results suggest that sawdust and marble dust can be used as low-cost hybrid fillers, although SEM analysis and replicated wear testing are needed for validation.

Keywords— Sawdust, Marble dust, Epoxy biocomposite, Waste-derived fillers, Wear testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sawdust and marble dust are low-cost waste materials that can be reused as fillers in polymer composites, supporting waste valorisation and circular material development [1].

Previous studies show that sawdust-based and mineral-filled composites can influence strength, water absorption and wear behaviour. This study investigates sawdust–marble dust epoxy biocomposites with different filler ratios to compare their physical, mechanical and wear performance [2].

II. METHODOLOGY

The SD/MD epoxy biocomposites were prepared by compression molding using sawdust, marble dust, epoxy resin and hardener.

A. Composite Preparation

Four composite samples were prepared: SD50MD10, SD45MD15, SD40MD20 and SD20MD40, using a fixed 40 wt.% epoxy binder. The sample codes indicate the filler content; for example, SD40MD20 contains 40 wt.% sawdust and 20 wt.% marble dusts.

B. Testing Procedure

The samples were tested for density, water absorption, compressive strength, flexural strength, Rockwell hardness and dry-sliding wear rate. Wear testing was carried out using an in-house pin-on-disc tribometer with a rotating stainless-steel counter-face disc, following the general ASTM G99 principle. The counter-face surface roughness was not measured in this study and is recommended for future reproducibility improvement.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SD/MD ratio influenced physical, mechanical and wear properties. SD40MD20 showed the best balance, with higher strength, hardness and the lowest wear rate. Water absorption decreased from 6.02% to 2.02% as sawdust content decreased. However, SD20MD40 showed lower compressive strength, indicating that excess marble dust may weaken matrix continuity. Table 1 summarizes density, water absorption, strength, hardness and average wear rate.

Table 1. Physical, mechanical and wear performance of SD/MD epoxy composites.

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Water Abs. (%)	Comp. Strength (MPa)	Flex. Strength (MPa)	Hardness (RHN)	Avg. Wear Rate (×10 ⁻⁶ g/m)
SD50MD10	1.18	6.02	48.57	33.31	47	7.02
SD45MD15	1.56	3.44	53.91	37.77	56	5.35
SD40MD20	1.78	2.85	57.54	49.87	63	5.01
SD20MD40	1.40	2.02	43.73	49.87	58	5.84

Figure 1. Wear-rate comparison of SD/MD epoxy composites and conventional brake-pad reference.

Figure 1 shows that SD40MD20 had the lowest wear rate among the developed composites, while the reference brake pad performed better.

IV. CONCLUSION

SD/MD epoxy biocomposites were developed using sawdust and marble dust. SD40MD20 showed the best overall performance. Future work should include SEM analysis, repeated wear tests and counter-face roughness measurement.

References

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